

Master Thesis
Environment and Resource Management

MARINE PLASTIC POLLUTION SCHEMES: BRINGING CLARITY IN AN EVOLVING LANDSCAPE

An analysis of claims and credits for collection and transformation of marine plastic debris and the point of view of small and medium enterprises.

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Foreword

This thesis is written as part of the MSc Environment and Resource Management at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam.

I have decided to write my final project about marine pollution as the ocean is one of my greatest passions. Even though the topic is in constant evolution, I hope this paper can contribute to the research about solutions to plastic pollution, to help protect and restore the oceans for all of us and for future generations.

I would like to thank my supervisors Hanna Dijkstra and Prof. Dr. Pieter van Beukering for their guidance during this project. Thank you to the people I interviewed and who shared with me useful and insightful information. And finally thank you to Nicolás for being my greatest supporter during this last year's adventure.

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Abstract

Marine plastic pollution is a wicked problem that needs to be addressed by multi-level governance approaches. As innovative solutions emerge from a variety of non-state actors, more NGOs and companies are creating new arrangements and adopting plastic claims in the form of credits, certifications and labeling schemes. While the current landscape is evolving and new instruments are being developed to meet the needs of different stakeholders, there is still a lack of standards and best practices. This raises questions of transparency and accountability, and makes it difficult to evaluate the real impact of those tools.

Even though a growing body of literature is looking at plastic governance, little has been specifically researched about marine plastic claims. This paper fills in this research gap through extensive literature review and semi-structured interviews to small-medium enterprises in the business of transforming marine plastic into valuable products. It provides a comparative assessment of existing arrangements and identifies to what extent they meet the needs of SMEs and startups. As a result, it identifies elements that, if implemented, have the potential to increase credibility and traceability of the system and to facilitate the uniform acceptance and application of marine plastic certifications and other schemes in business.

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List of abbreviations

CoC: Chain of Custody
CSR: Corporate Social Responsibility
NGOs: Non-Governmental Organizations
OBP: Ocean-bound plastic
SMEs: Small Medium Enterprises

Note on terminology

1. The term *marine plastic* is used in this paper to indicate plastic into the ocean or at risk of entering the ocean, therefore the type of plastic targeted by the arrangements studied in this research.
2. The terms *mechanisms*, *arrangements* and *schemes* are used in this paper interchangeably to refer to the different non-governmental schemes and programs that aim at preventing and reducing marine plastic pollution: standards, certifications, plastic credits schemes, labels and trademarks, supply chain solutions.

1. Introduction and problem definition

Since the 1950s, the use of plastic has been increasing exponentially, mainly driven by the material's advantages in terms of versatility, light weight, durability and low cost (Beckman, 2018; World Economic Forum et al., 2006). Plastic has been rapidly accumulating in the environment as a consequence of growing demand for the material, its non-biodegradability and mismanagement of waste worldwide (Dauvergne, 2018; Schmaltz et al., 2020). These facts have led to increasing concerns about environmental and human health and the economic costs of pollution (Vince & Hardesty, 2017). Plastic pollution statistics are alarming: approximately 8.3 billion metric tons of virgin plastic have been produced worldwide and 6.3 billion metric tons have become plastic waste. Of that, only 9% has ever been recycled. The remaining 81% is accumulating in landfills or in the natural environment as litter (79%), or it was incinerated (12%) (Geyer et al., 2017). If present trends continue, it is estimated that by 2050 there will be 12 billion metric tons of plastic in landfills (Geyer et al., 2017).

This research focuses on the problem of the accumulation of plastics in the marine environment, where plastic represents the most common type of anthropogenic debris by making up at least 80% of the total waste in marine litter surveys (UNEP, 2014). Pollution sources are diffuse and fragmented unevenly across regions and socioeconomic groups (Dauvergne, 2018), but studies agree that over 80% of the total marine waste comes from land-based sources (UNEP, 2014). The remaining 20% comes from marine-based activities such as cruise lines, fishing and shipping (UNEP, 2014). It is also estimated that 150 million metric tons of plastic were already circulating in the marine environment in 2016 (World Economic Forum, Ellen MacArthur Foundation and McKinsey & Company, 2016) and at least additionally 8 million tons end up in our oceans every year (Boucher & Friot, 2017).

Available literature demonstrates the negative social, ecological and economic impact of marine plastic pollution by researching about animals ingesting plastics and being entangled in ghost nets, loss of revenues from tourism and fish catch, loss in quality of livelihoods in coastal communities and increased costs deriving from cleaning activities (Ten Brink et al., 2009). A particular concern has developed in recent years towards microplastics, smaller pieces of plastic debris not visible to the naked eye (Andrady, 2011). The total economic cost of marine plastic pollution is still unknown, but it is estimated that plastic debris is damaging marine ecosystems at a cost of approximately US\$13 billion per year (UNEP, 2014). Although there is evidence that policies targeting such debris can be cost-effective (UNEP, 2014), especially if they focus on preventing and avoiding the costs deriving from pollution (Raubenheimer & Mcilgorm, 2017), global efforts seem to be scattered and uncoordinated. While studies about marine plastic governance have so far focused on those economic and ecological aspects, only limited literature, even though growing, is researching new governance solutions. As many other environmental problems, marine plastic pollution is a transboundary issue that needs to be tackled with innovative governance solutions from different actors (Vince & Hardesty, 2017). From the governmental side, there is a lack of international regulations addressed to land-based and marine pollution, and national laws are not enough to face such a complex issue. On the other hand, the private sector is showing a growing interest in contributing to

the marine debris concern and more private organizations and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are making commitments to address the issue, by reducing the use of plastic in their production processes, emphasizing circular economy and creating new products made of recycled terrestrial and marine plastics (Vince & Hardesty, 2017). They represent emerging sustainable business models that are trying to capture the attention of the public and at the same time provide an environmental service (Dijkstra et al., 2020).

As a consequence of the evolution of civil society and private sector response to marine plastic management, new voluntary instruments to validate plastic materials based on their source or on the way they are processed have arisen in recent years. This tendency has resulted in the emergence of a variety of standards, certifications and credit programs related to accounting for ocean plastic or circular plastic (The Circulate Initiative, 2021). However, existing plastic claims are still not widely applied and do not follow homogeneous standards. Additionally, unclarity about basic guidelines, such as the existence of numerous definitions of what is considered to be ocean plastic and ocean-bound plastic (OBP) (Dijkstra et al., 2021; The Circulate Initiative, 2021), adds complexity to an already wicked problem.

1.1. Research objectives and questions

To address the research gap in claims and programs for marine plastic and their effectiveness, this paper describes the state-of-the-art of existing governance arrangements offered by the private sectors and civil society. The objective is to provide lessons about the potentialities and challenges of self-regulatory industry measures to tackle marine plastic pollution, and to understand if those instruments match the needs of small-medium enterprises (SMEs) and add value to their activities.

This research paper aims at addressing the following main question: *what is the current landscape of existing voluntary governance arrangements for marine plastic?*

The sub-questions identified are:

- *How can those arrangements be compared and evaluated, and how do they perform according to a set of evaluating criteria?*
- *What are the barriers to adoption and the enabling factors from the point of view of SMEs?*

2. Literature review and conceptual framework

2.1. Marine litter as a reverse common

Marine litter has been defined by the United Nations Environment as “any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment. Marine litter consists of items that have been made or used by people and deliberately discarded into the sea or rivers or on beaches; brought indirectly to the sea with rivers, sewage, stormwater or winds; accidentally lost, including material lost at sea in bad weather[...]; or deliberately left by people on beaches and shores” (UNEP, 2009, p. 13). Plastic debris is the main source of litter in our oceans, and it is agreed in literature that it presents the characteristics of a wicked problem (a problem that lacks clarity in its aims and solutions (Rittel & Webber, 1973)), and more specifically it has been defined as a wicked problem within a global ocean common (Landon-Lane, 2018; Vince & Hardesty, 2018). Even though Hardin was outlining extractive dynamics in his theory about the global commons (Hardin, 1968), marine plastic debris can be seen as a reverse common, where the problem is not extraction but pollution. This means that the lack of a governance system that defines and imposes rules for behavior, drives individuals to consider the global shared cost of polluting smaller than the cost of paying for one’s own waste (Landon-Lane, 2018).

Because a wide variety of actors, state and non-state, are responsible for and involved in marine pollution, assigning different levels of responsibilities and have them pay based on a polluter-pay principle does not seem a reasonable or achievable solution. Similarly, privatization and introduction of property rights have been used as common solutions to wicked environmental problems, but they do not apply to marine plastic: marine debris is detached from its sources, it crosses international and open waters, and an allocation pollution quota among polluters would be difficult to establish and enforce (Landon-Lane, 2018). To add complexity, the global governance of plastic seems to be characterized by weak institutions, fragmented and uneven regulations, uncoordinated policies (Dauvergne, 2018) and inability to provide effective solutions. There is a large gap in international laws, especially regarding land-based plastic marine pollution and areas beyond national jurisdiction (Vince & Hardesty, 2017), and regional and national laws are scattered and heterogeneous. In a context where various stakeholders have different goals, interests, powers and responsibilities, it is more plausible to look at the issue as a global shared responsibility, and solutions to the problem should be based on collaborative efforts (Landon-Lane, 2018; Ten Brink et al., 2009; Wisz et al., 2020; World Economic Forum et al., 2006).

2.2. The role of civil society and the private sector. CSR and sustainable business models

Based on these premises, it is clear that marine plastic represents a governance problem. Like the majority of issues related to natural resources, it is also a complex problem: it crosses natural and administrative boundaries, and involves a variety of state and non-state actors with

multiple and different objectives, interests, degrees of power and resources (Nunan, 2018). As such, it cannot be solved by traditional governance models (Vince & Hardesty, 2017). To be tackled it needs an interactive and multi-tiered governance system that can be described as multi-level. In multi-level governance, the idea of governance relates to the interactive action towards shared objectives of multiple independent public and private actors, at different administrative levels and geographic scales (Armitage, 2007; Nunan, 2018; V.D. Grijp & Brander, 2002). Based on those assumptions, literature agrees that effective solutions, require the right mix of regulation, market mechanisms and community-based efforts (Ostrom et al., 2002; Vince & Hardesty, 2017).

In this developing context, an important role in finding alternative tools and approaches to traditional governance is played by NGOs and the private sector with the emergence of new business models. Business models represent an organization's underlying core logic and strategic choices, used to create and capture value within a network (Shafer et al., 2005). The concept has evolved in literature and business application, and the new notion of sustainable business model has emerged. Sustainable business models add novelty to traditional ones by incorporating concepts, principles and goals that aim at sustainability, or by integrating sustainability into their value proposition, creation, capture and delivery (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). This concept is often associated with innovation and with sustainable entrepreneurship, the former defined as "a way to increase competitive advantage, but also a means to improve environmental or social sustainability" and the latter as "the pursuit of creating a successful, new business, while also providing environmental and social benefits to a range of stakeholders" (Dijkstra et al., 2021, p. 2). A further evolution to the concept of business models, together with an increasingly pressing need to tackle environmental problems, societal and economic challenges, has driven the emergency of circular business models, linked to the notion of Circular Economy. A Circular Economy is "an industrial system that is restorative and regenerative by design. It rests on three main principles: preserving and enhancing natural capital, optimizing resource yields, and fostering system effectiveness" (World Economic Forum et al., 2006, p. 32). Underpinned and aligned with such principles is the concept of New Plastic Economy, a proposal with the vision that plastic never becomes waste, but it re-enters the economy as a valuable technical or biological nutrient, and it does so by creating an after-use plastics economy (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2016). This notion derives from a focus on plastic packaging material, but we reckon that this framework might also be applied to other sources of plastic. In the context of marine plastic management, the pillar of creating an after-use economy is especially important. We note that growing consumer awareness and the increase of voluntary commitments from companies offer a direct incentive to build more collection and recovery infrastructure, and to use plastic waste to create new products by upcycling. In this emerging market, plastic is given a higher value and consumer demand can stimulate a systemic industry change (World Economic Forum et al., 2006)

While those concepts can be applied to any corporation, SMEs and startups have proven to be more flexible and prone to innovate (Guo & Cao, 2014; Matejun, 2014), making them an important focal point of studies in marine plastic management. Dijkstra et al. (2021) carried out the first comprehensive study of entrepreneurs and SMEs that provide solutions to the

marine plastic problem; they categorize them according to four functions: prevention, collection, monitoring and transformation (Dijkstra et al., 2021). A section of this paper will look at companies engaged in transformation, directly or through their network, to investigate their point of view about certifications and how they could be more extensively adopted.

The growing interest of companies in solutions to environmental problems is linked to the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). CSR can be defined as a self-regulating business practice adopted by companies to be more socially accountable to themselves, their stakeholders, and the public (Fernando, 2021), and it is a form of corporate behavior beyond government regulation (Landon-Lane, 2018). CSR, together with business ethics, has been defined by stakeholder theories. According to such theories, a business can be understood as a set of relationships among groups that have a stake in the activities that make up the business, and considering those actors allows a company to jointly create and trade value (Parmar et al., 2010). Companies are therefore accountable not only to their shareholders but to all stakeholders, who influence and are influenced by the activities of the company (Ellerup Nielsen & Thomsen, 2007). Since the past few years companies involved in the life-cycle of plastic have been gradually incorporating social demands for solutions to the plastic problem into the core of their business and they have been framing their internal governance as following principles of responsibility and sustainability (Dauvergne, 2018). From biodegradable bags to plastic-free packaging and recycled materials, companies are addressing the growing global concern for plastic. CSR as a solution to the plastic debris issue has been criticized in its traditional view for being profit-driven and instrumental to gain consumer confidence (Ellerup Nielsen & Thomsen, 2007; Friedman, 1970), while declaring instead to be generated from commitment to social and environmental issues (Dauvergne, 2018). However, CSR limitations can be alleviated by integration with a multi-governance approach, that can benefit from some degree of state regulation. CSR systems also have the advantage of driving industry best practices and give legitimacy to the institutions and companies adopting them (Vince & Hardesty, 2017). It is important to critically assess those instruments but, under the correct conditions, they have the potential to promote social and environmental sustainability.

2.3. Voluntary arrangements as a form of CSR

A very common form of CSR is represented by voluntary codes of conduct, certifications and offsetting schemes (for example using carbon credit trading), meant to promote and highlight environmental and socially sound practices. They provide consumers with guidance and differentiate from competitors that try to acquire a green reputation without real changes in their productive processes (Dosi & Moretto, 2001). The most recent types of voluntary arrangements are developed by non-state actors, for example NGOs, social groups, private associations (Auld et al., 2008). Most of them have been taking inspiration from similar initiatives such as the forestry sector, fisheries and palm oil production.

Governance arrangements for marine plastic are still scattered but they are acquiring relevance, and are often mentioned in literature as one of the possible contributions to the marine plastic problem (Landon-Lane, 2018; Raubenheimer & Mcilgorm, 2017). Theories

propose the establishment of an international body to coordinate these measures (Landon-Lane, 2018; Raubenheimer & Mcilgorm, 2017), supported by the establishment of transparent, stable and environmentally sustainable end-markets for plastic waste (Raubenheimer & Mcilgorm, 2017). However, there is unclarity about how such standards and mechanisms are developed and under which criteria, and there is a research gap regarding barriers to adoption and factors that enable companies, especially SMEs, to adopt them.

2.4. Integrating concepts into a framework

Governance and stakeholder theories, linked to business models, represent the basis of this research. The conceptual framework in Figure 1 visualizes a holistic governance approach to the reduction of marine plastic litter (Vince & Hardesty, 2018), highlighting tools and approaches available to sustainable and circular business models: stakeholder influence, CSR and third-party certifications. A special focus is given to companies engaged in transformation of ocean plastic. In this context, this paper researches voluntary governance arrangements for marine plastic.

Figure 1. Visualization of conceptual framework. Adapted from Dijkstra et al., 2021; Vince & Hardesty, 2018

3. Methodology

A mixed-methodology was used for this research. Qualitative and descriptive research methods are suited to the nature of the research gap and the diversity and heterogeneity of the instruments studied. However, to systematically compare governance mechanisms, a semi-quantitative scoring has been adopted. Figure 2 provides a methodological framework with visualization of every step of the approach taken.

Figure 2. Methodological framework.

3.1. Research strategy and criteria development

The first step of the research adopted a literature review methodology, to classify the variety of existing non-governmental programs available for organizations to verify their claims about collecting and recycling activities, final or intermediate products, or to offset their plastic footprint. Data collection was undertaken between March and June 2021 and, due to the nature of the study, the investigation was mainly conducted in grey literature, such as certification bodies' and companies' websites and reports, sustainability websites and online newspapers. The main outcome was the creation of a database of existing mechanisms. As it will be further elaborated, the database categorizes arrangements into:

- Standards and certifications: documents that provide guidelines and written assurance that the product or system in question meets certain requirements.
- Plastic credit schemes: CSR mechanisms that generate credits that entitle a right to offset a certain amount of plastic.
- Supply chain solutions: a different range of programs linked to the creation of supply chains for the market of plastic waste.

In parallel, a set of 11 criteria were developed to evaluate and compare mechanisms (Table 1) WWF's Principles for Effective and Credible Certification Schemes (WWF, 2009) and ISEAL

Credibility Principles included in the ISEAL Standard Setting Code (ISEAL, 2014) were used as **guiding criteria** and adapted to the scope of the research and the information collected in the database. Those guiding principles are detailed in Appendix A. Additional criteria were developed independently because considered relevant from the point of view of SMEs.

Table 1. Overview of guiding criteria and the 11 criteria developed.

Guiding criteria	Criteria
Sustainability, continuous improvement, result-oriented, relevant scale and relevance	Monitoring and evaluating - Impact
	Monitoring and evaluating - Reporting
	Monitoring and evaluating - Continuous improvement
Transparency, truthfulness, traceability, accessibility	Definition of plastic targeted
	Definition of requirements and procedures - Robust process
	Technology and traceability
	Chain of custody
Commitment to reducing key issues, efficiency, rigor, compliant with international framework	Integration with other schemes
Third-party independent verification	Third-party independent verification
n/a	Cost of certifications or conversion measure for credits
n/a	Visibility in media

3.2. Data collection

The information needed for the evaluation was gathered in the ways listed below:

1. websites and document centers;
2. other online sources;
3. documents requests through websites' contact forms;
4. contact via email;
5. one interview with a certification body.

For each arrangement, the top listed sources were consulted first, and if insufficient information was available, further data sources were used.

To answer the second sub-question, data was collected through semi-structured interviews with 6 SMEs engaged in transformation (Table 2). Qualitative interviews are useful when knowledge is situational and depends on context (Sayrs, 1998), and are therefore considered the ideal method to understand the SMEs' point of view. Finding from this section also allow validation through triangulation of data. By using different sources of information and multiple perspectives to study a phenomenon, triangulation provides multiple contexts to enrich the understanding of the problem or research questions (Guion et al., 2011).

Table 2. Overviews of interviewees.

Company description and activities	Company size	Location of activities (collection, transformation, processing)	Final products	Main markets of upcycled product	Interviewee
Social enterprise for collection and manufacturing.	11-50 employees	Sri Lanka	Bags and accessories	Europe	Co-founder
Profit company and foundation for collection and manufacturing.	11-50 employees	Indonesia (soon to be implemented)	Bracelets	Europe	Founder
Profit company, marketplace for ocean recycled plastic materials.	2-10 employees	Collecting and recycling: Indonesia, Philippines, Thailand. Processing: China, Taiwan, Vietnam.	Raw materials	Europe and USA	Founder
Profit company for collection and manufacturing.	2-10 employees	Europe, processing in South East Asia	Yoga mats	Europe	Co-founder
Profit company for collection, recycling, manufacturing.	11-50 employees	Southeast Asia	Bags	Europe	Founder
Profit company for collection, recycling, manufacturing.	11-50 employees	Worldwide, manufacturing in Europe	Bracelets	Europe	Ethics manager

Finally, a follow-up survey developed with the tool Qualtrics was sent to all the interviewees. The survey lists the evaluation criteria in Table 1 and asks the respondents to rate them based on their subjective importance. The scoring system uses a Likert scale with 5 scale points: not important–slightly important–neutral–important– very important. Results were collected and analyzed using both basic statistics and qualitative interpretation.

3.3. Data analysis and scoring

A semi-quantitative scoring guide was developed to facilitate evaluation and comparison. The detailed scoring system is provided as Supplementary Material at the end of this paper. The guide includes a rubric for each criteria made of a set of questions, and a scoring system -1 (negative judgment), 0 (neutral), +1 (positive, best practice). Separate rubrics were developed for each type of arrangement, however, for some criteria, the same rubric applied to multiple

categories. For example, the criteria of *Third-party independent* verification evaluates standards and certifications based on independent auditing requirements, while it evaluates credit schemes and supply chain solutions based on those arrangements being or not being certified. On the other hand, some criteria do not apply to certain schemes.

For scoring, the same sources used for data collection were employed. For completeness, webinars, YouTube channels, social media and podcasts from the organizations were also taken into consideration as a source of information to be verified. Atlas.ti was used to inspect standards and annual reports, using a pre-defined coding approach that enabled to analyze the documents methodologically. The advantage of this methodology lies in the possibility to create a structured and pre-defined group of topics that are relevant to the RQ.

Finally, the interviews' transcripts were analyzed and linked to the results of the scoring system, to develop the point of view and experience of SMEs and start-ups concerning marine plastic arrangements.

4. Results: desk research and comparison of arrangements

4.1. Current landscape

To date, there is no scientific or grey literature that provides a complete overview of non-state governance arrangements for marine plastic, even though a few studies have emerged about the limitations of those programs. This research maps the current landscape by covering most programs available at the time of the analysis known to the researcher. Based on the scope of this research, they have been categorized into:

- Standards and certifications;
- Plastic credit schemes;
- Supply chain solutions.

Companies providing technological solutions and programs that do not directly target marine plastic are considered out of scope. However, four programs that do not only target marine plastic were included in the research because 1) a significant part of their activity targets plastic from bodies of water, 2) they focus on marine plastic prevention, 3) the location of their activities is mainly on islands or coastlines. A total of 18 arrangements were identified, selected, and included in the database, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Overview of arrangements identified and used in the research.

Arrangement name			Arrangement Initiator	Ocean or ocean bound plastic (OBP) specific	Arrangement type			
					Standard	Certification	Plastic credit scheme	Supply chain solution
OBP Certification Program	OBP Neutrality subprogram	OBP Neutralization Services Provider Standard	Zero Plastic Oceans	√	√	x		
		OBP Plastic Producers & Users Standard		√	√	√		
	OBP Recycling subprogram	OBP collection organization standard		√	√	√		
		OBP recycling organization standard		√	√	√		
OceanCycle			OceanCycle	√	√	√		
Recycled material certification blue			PFI Fareast	√	√	√		
Public standard for plastics retrieved from the hydrosphere			DNV	No, any body of water	√	√		
Ocean Plastic Standard			The Ocean Cleanup	√	√			
Plastic waste reduction standard			Verra	No, but relevant for credit schemes	√	√		
Cleanhub			Cleanhub	No, but focused on preventing ocean pollution	√			√
Parley Ocean Plastic			Parley for the Oceans	√				√
Oceanworks			Oceanworks	Partially, 5 categories out of 7 are related				√
Ocean Waste Plastics			Pack Tech	√				√
#tide			Tide Ocean	√				√
Plastic Bank			Plastic Bank	√			√	√
The Plastic Collective			The Plastic Collective	No, but majority of operation is located on islands			√	√
Plastics For Change			Plastics For Change	√			√	√
ReSEA Project			ReSEA Project	√			√	

The landscape of arrangements for marine plastic materials is nascent, with most programs introduced between 2018 and 2020. Figure 3 shows the cumulative number of arrangements in this paper, by year. This newness in the governance system and the related lack of standardization mean that the concepts are developing and changing over time.

Figure 3. Cumulative number of arrangements for marine plastic.

The business form of the mechanism setters also varies among NGOs, social enterprises, and profit companies (public or private) (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Overview of arrangements by business form.

While profit companies and NGOs are well-established business forms, social enterprises are newer in the organizations' landscape. As Fernando (2017) described, “social enterprise is a management practice that integrates principles of private enterprise with social sector goals and objectives”, designed to have a positive long-term social impact for individuals and communities.

This overview shows how those schemes are multi-governance and their initiators have different scopes and objectives. The network they create also involves organizations, companies and individuals at different levels of the supply chain of plastic, from informal waste pickers to corporations that use labels in their final products. Figure 5 provides a visual representation, showing that 47% of the schemes do not fall only under one category but provide different solutions. Additionally, standards and certifications are an overarching category under which other arrangements can operate. They can be used in different steps of the supply chain, and to certify credit schemes and final products.

Figure 5. Overview of arrangements classified by type.

Labels and trademarks represent a strong motivation for companies to adopt certain mechanisms, however, they are not separately listed in the categorization of schemes, because they are always associated with other categories. For clarity, they will be briefly explained at the end of this section, where each type of arrangement is introduced.

Standards and certifications

A standard is a “document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results[...]” (ISO, 2004). Setting international standards is a complex task especially in certain environments and industries, such as the governance of marine plastic, since the practices the standards targets are relatively new, not widely diffused and coordinated.

“Certification is the provision by an independent body of written assurance that the product, service or system in question meets specific requirements” (ISO, 2021). Certifications are a form of communication along the supply chain (Dankers, 2003), they guide consumers and validate the material that is purchased or marketed with a claim, generally based on its source or the way it is processed (The Circulate Initiative, 2021). In the case of ocean plastic, the criteria of the source is commonly used. An organization or project can comply with a standard but lack certification. A key actor in this mechanism is the verification body, generally a third-party “without direct interest in the economic relationship between the supplier and buyer” (Dankers, 2003, p. 8)

Standards and certifications can be further categorized based on what they certify: 1) the supply chain of plastic from a certain origin, or 2) the collection and/or recycling of plastic to generate, sell, and buy plastic credits. Within each group, there are significant differences, mainly related to requirements and procedures, the actors targeted and the businesses covered. Table 4 provides an example.

Table 4. Example of programs and different businesses covered.

Program		Businesses covered under the standard
OBP Recycling subprogram	Collection organizations standard	Collection, storage/sorting, bailing, transport.
OBP Recycling subprogram	Recycling organizations standard	Storage/sorting, bailing, transport, sorting/grinding/washing, extrusion/molding, recycled product.
OceanCyle certification		Collection, aggregation, processing, manufacturing
Plastics collected in the hydrosphere		Extraction, transportation, recycling/disposal/recovery, manufacturing, sales.

Plastic credits and offsetting

Plastic offset and credit schemes are mechanisms that generate credits that entitle their holders to offset a certain amount of plastic they generate (The Circulate Initiative, 2021).

More specifically, plastic credits are “a transferrable unit representing a specific quantity of plastic that has been collected and possibly recycled from the environment. [...] The term “plastic offsetting” refers to purchases of plastic credits generated through activities that reduce the stock of plastic pollution in nature”(WWF, 2021, p. 2). Those programs are relatively new and were introduced by organizations to provide companies with the possibility to balance their plastic footprint by removing plastic from the environment (WWF, 2021).

Supply chain solutions

Supply chain solutions is a term developed specifically for the purpose of this research, and it refers to a separate group of arrangements that includes the creation of a supply chain for the market of plastic waste, banking systems, new technologies for recycling and processing waste, and marketplaces for plastic materials. Moreover, most of those programs act on the supply chain, but at the same time provide other mechanisms, as shown in Figure 6. The most common example is the creation of a supply chain of plastic, linked with a crediting scheme.

Figure 6. Description of supply chain stages covered by each arrangement. Impact amplifier refers to the organization receiving payments for the removal of plastic from the environment (for example, for every \$0.50 purchased in the marketplace, 1 kg of ocean plastic is removed. Add \$0.50/KG to your car to double this quantity(Oceanworks, 2021)).

Labels and trademarks

A label is a visual identifier of certain characteristics of a material or its origin, and is applied to the product sold, while trademarks are “recognizable insignia, phrase, symbol or word that denotes a specific product and legally differentiate it from all other products of its kind” (Investopedia, 2021). Labels can be provided by certified or not certified bodies. Certifications labels indicate that compliance with a certain standard is verified and they can be controlled by the standard-setting body or by the certification body itself, if the certification body certifies against its own standard (Dankers, 2003). “Labelling products with a [...] logo provides guidance for consumers on the market to make more informed choices based on product sustainability”

(PFI Fareast, 2021, p. 7) and often enables firms to command a price premium (Bleda & Valente, 2009; Blomquist et al., 2015). 72% of the mechanisms analyzed offer their own label or trademark.

4.2. Comparison and evaluation criteria

Even though certifications and credit schemes are becoming increasingly popular, the lack of a shared governance system and standards raises doubts and criticism to their ability to meet their goals and to play a role in solving environmental issues. This section presents the results of the evaluation and comparison of the arrangements, according to the criteria in Table 1 and based on the guiding system included in the Supplementary Material. For each criteria, main findings and a brief discussion are provided in the following sub-sections.

It is important to note that the results are based on information publicly available in grey literature and the results do not necessarily mean that the company does not comply with some criteria, but that those are not communicated in online sources, or it was not possible to obtain them by getting in contact with the organizations.

4.2.1. Monitoring and evaluating systems - Impact and reporting

Monitoring and evaluating systems are the “ongoing process through which an organization draws conclusions about its contribution to intended outcomes and impacts. [It] consists of a set of interconnected functions, processes and activities, including systematic collection of monitoring data on specified indicators and the implementation of outcome and impact evaluations” (ISEAL, 2014, p. 7). Companies tackling marine plastic pollution and its sources are looking at the plastic issue non only from an environmental point of view, but also from a social-economical angle. This integrated approach is embedded in the concept of sustainable development, namely “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Bruntland Gro., 1987, p. 41). This concept considers social, economic and environmental issues as interdependent and inseparable components of human progress (European Commission, n.d.). Most of the marine plastic arrangements aim at taking this concept into practice. Table 5 provides examples of sustainability aspects covered by the different mechanisms.

Table 5. Examples of sustainability aspects covered under the concept of sustainable development. Source: (OECD, 2010) and arrangements analyzed in this paper.

Sustainability aspects	Elaboration	Examples and arrangements
Environmental impacts	Plastic pollution, climate, biodiversity, land use, environmental consequences of firms and consumers (it leads to more sustainable production and consumption), waste production - generation, -recycling, animal welfare.	Recover non-recyclables because they represent most of all ocean plastic, increase plastic recovery rates in critical regions, use of recovery methods with the lowest environmental impact possible, develop waste management standards (Cleanhub).
Social Impacts	Labor conditions, slavery, child labor, standards related to job quality, social inclusion and protection of particular groups, gender equality, treatment and opportunities, non-discrimination, health and safety, educational systems.	OceanCyle does social auditing in the collection communities, employing surveys to understand communities' needs and barriers to work. They provide food, shelter improvements, protective gear, support improvements in nutrition, health and school enrollment (OceanCycle).
Economic impacts	Creation of market in informal economies, trade, competitiveness, innovation, introduction and dissemination of new technologies - production methods - products), impact on specific regions, economic growth and employment.	Encourage the growth of micro and small enterprises in the formal waste collection sector (OBP Recycling Organization Standard).

81% of the schemes mention the environmental impact of their activities, mainly related to the reduction of plastic pollution and of its effect on the oceans, rivers, and animals, and 69% of the also include a social aspect. 13% only declare an environmental intention and 19% do not make any claim related to any of the sustainable development aspects, or just mention compliance with legislations and common standards, such as no-child labor and no discrimination¹. Supply chain solutions are the most focused on the social impact of their activities, in terms of improved working and living conditions of the people involved in the supply chain, while the standard setters tend to communicate more about their environmental impact.

It can be observed that, even though most schemes mention elements of environmental, social and economic impact, those impacts are used as baseline for strategy-setting and storytelling. Impact metrics are commonly displayed on the website of the organizations, but there is a significant gap in the quantification of those impacts. Because of the lack of a standardized

¹ Those numbers use a total of 16 arrangements, as Zero Plastic Ocean's certifications are considered as one.

impact measuring system, even the most established programs lack trustworthy monitoring and evaluating systems, that go beyond communication as a marketing tool. This lack of measurability and full impact traceability is reflected in the scarcity of impact reports available. Excluding the arrangements established in 2021, where an impact report cannot be yet provided, only two organizations publish a proper document where their impact is quantifiable and include plans for the following years. For programs founded in 2019 and 2020, a first-year report should be available and mention the recurrence of further publications.

Cleanhub sets an interesting example by providing a live tracking system with impact progress by customer, showing details regarding the amount of plastic collection that the company has financed, the details of the collection partners, collection procedures and recovery live updates. Even though this enhances traceability in impact, the system could benefit from an overview of the overall impact provided by the mechanism, trackable by year of activity. Another example is provided by The Ocean Cleanup that, in collaboration with DNV, has recently (May 2021) disclosed the amount of plastic recovered and certified it under this standard.

4.2.2. Monitoring and evaluating systems – Continuous improvement

Standards setters and certification bodies are supposed to seek to understand their impact and demonstrate progress towards their intended outcomes (ISEAL, 2014). Monitoring and evaluating systems must be linked to the content of the arrangements and must evolve over time. Best practices are found in arrangements that set a fixed period for the claim to be valid, and for the certification label or certificate to be used. The specific duration has also to be accompanied by revision procedures. The time limit of the validity of claims makes it possible to adapt the criteria to new developments and insights that may emerge, and this way enabling the system to evolve and improve over time (V.D. Grijp & Brander, 2002).

Only two out of the six standards and certifications analyzed meet this criteria, by setting a duration for its certification or setting a plastic crediting period. Additionally, they also set a date for the next revision of the standard. Two other arrangements set a time-bound validity but do not mention any scheduled revision of the standard, even though the standard has been updated at least twice over time. Finally, two mechanisms do not have a review in place, scoring low in continuous improvement. Examples are provided in Table 6.

Table 6. Example of programs and different approaches to continuous improvement.

Type of arrangement	Program	Example
Standard	Plastic Waste Reduction Standard	A plastic crediting period is defined, and the next review of the standard is set.
Certification	OceanCycle	The certification lasts for 12 months and every shipment of material is checked and approved. But there is no publicly available process to revise the standard and no indication of the next review.
Standard	Public standard for plastics retrieved from the hydrosphere	No review system is in place and publicly available.

Continuous improvement is strictly linked to stakeholder engagement. Meaningful and equitable stakeholder participation, that considers different stakeholders at multiple levels in the development and evolution of the arrangement, is a fundamental aspect of any governance solution. The Plastic Program by Verra provides a best practice in inclusion of different stakeholders: the standard was established with the support of a multi-stakeholder committee, with smaller assessment working groups, leading organizations in the sector of recycled plastic, a group of technical advisors and Verra board. An advisory group will also monitor the evolution of the program, responding to new activities that might emerge in the market and the methodology was open before publishing for a public comment period. For other programs, it was not possible to properly assess stakeholder engagement, as it is considered arbitrary to measure the criteria only based on publicly available information. I conclude that, if the collaboration from multiple actors is not publicly declared, it is not possible to assume that no consultation was in place when the arrangement was developed.

4.2.3. Plastic targeted, robust process, technology and traceability, chain of custody

The four criteria grouped in this section are related to the overarching concepts of transparency, truthfulness, traceability and accessibility. Risks related to the lack of those elements are associated with the whole value chain, starting from the moment when plastic is discarded until it is reprocessed into a new raw material or upcycled product. Especially the first steps of the chain provide opportunities for informal operations and this is why organizations mentioning transparency in their business model are often talking about the role of the informal waste sector and aim to “create an informal recycling economy, setting up collection networks that pay people fairly for what they collect” (OceanCycle, 2021).

Definition of plastic targeted

The arrangements analyzed target different types of plastic, that can be clustered based on the recyclability of the materials and their origin. Most programs target recyclable plastic, as it can be upcycled into new valuable products. Only Cleanhub, the OBP Neutrality Subprogram and Verra's Plastic Program include non-recyclable plastic in their scope. While there is a clear differentiation between recyclable and not recyclable plastic, there is unclarity about the origin of the plastic targeted. Criticism has been raised about the non-consistent definition of ocean plastic (Dijkstra et al., 2021; Ruffo & Martin, 2020; The Circulate Initiative, 2021), but a detailed overview of this heterogeneity had been not provided yet. Table 7 identifies 9 different plastic collection areas and 4 sub-areas for OBP, and the arrangements targeting them. Figure 7 provides a visual representation of the arrangements by type of plastic targeted.

Table 7. Plastic collection areas and origin of plastic claimed by arrangement.

Plastic collection areas	Definition	Arrangements
Ocean-bound plastic	Ocean-bound plastic defined according to the common definition by Jenna Jambek (57): abandoned plastic waste located within the range of 50km from shore in communities or areas where waste management is inexistent or very inefficient (Appendix B)	OceanCycle, Plastic Bank
	Ocean-bound plastic but with a difference in the distance from the coast (10km)	#tide
	Ocean-bound plastic according to Jambek (2015) definition, but further divided into three sub-categories (potential OBP, waterways OBP, shoreline OBP) (Appendix C)	OBP Certifications
	Ocean-bound plastic (not specified) and land waste	Cleanhub, Plastics For Change
Coastal plastic		Recycled material certification blue.
Any body of water (each deriving certification specified the body of water)		Public standard for plastics retrieved from the hydrosphere
Plastic from the Great Pacific Garbage Patch		Ocean Plastic Standard
Oceans and rivers around Jakarta, Indonesia		Ocean Waste Plastic, ReSEA Project
Plastic (from 7 specific types of plastic) in nature, including ocean, or that will likely end up in nature due to lack of collection systems		Plastic waste reduction standard
Plastic at risk of entering the oceans or plastic from beaches and coastal communities		Parley Ocean Plastic
Seven ad-hoc categories, five of which are ocean-plastic (including ocean-bound according to Jambek (2015) definition, plus two post-consumer recycled content under the names of averted and post-industrial recycled plastic (Appendix D)		Oceanworks

Figure 7. Overview of arrangements by type and by type of plastic targeted.

This lack of clear definitions creates problems of transparency for both consumers and companies. There is risk related to programs being able to use a “customized” definition of ocean or OBP for marketing purposes, where the origin of the plastic is not verifiable. Even though the term ocean plastic is commonly used for external communications, most of the mechanisms target OBP or plastic on land close to coastal communities. This happens because acting on ocean plastic is less efficient than on OBP, as more technologies are needed for recovery, and recovery is more expensive (plastic that is not floating cannot be easily captured and degraded plastic is more difficult to recycle, especially in mechanical recycling processes).

Another unregulated aspect is related to final products manufactured using recovered plastic materials. Claims must specify the minimum amount of recycled plastic from a specific origin that has to be included in the final product for the use of labels, certification labels and trademarks. Lacking a common standard, this percentage ranges from 100% to 5%, and this number is often not transparently communicated to consumers. In some cases, the program initiator sells raw material 100% from a certain source, but it is the manufacturer that defines the quantity of recycled content to use in the final product. In other instances, the program initiator sells plastic as raw material and in parallel develops a private label for its products, where the material used is 100% recycled. To add complexity, we also encounter one standard (The Ocean Plastic Standard), that does not specify content requirements. It is at the moment used only for a type of product (sunglasses), but it not clear if the same standard might be used to certify other items with different content.

Robust process

The appraisal of process robustness applies in this instance only to certifications and standards. Companies selling final products and providers of supply chain solutions do not follow a standardized process, unless certified. This problem is related to the transparency of a system based on voluntary actions. Standard and certifications follow robust procedures, therefore the problem detected not the lack of robustness, but the lack of adoption of standards and certification schemes by other arrangements such as credit schemes. The main differences among certification schemes reside in the public availability of documentation that describes standards and procedures in place (Table 8). While, for example, OBP Certification Program's procedures are publicly available on the website, OceanCyle does not provide a document center, and standards are available only on request. There is also unclarity about The Ocean Plastic Standard, where no documentation is available but there is the possibility to consult the Hydrosphere Standard, which was used as the baseline for its development.

Table 8. Example of programs and process robustness.

Type of arrangement	Program	Example
Certification	Recycled material certification blue	Documents are easily accessible and complete.
Standard and certification	OceanCyle	There is a process and some requirements are mentioned, but documentation is not publicly available.
Supply chain solutions	Plastic Bank	No requirements for robust process, as it does not follow any standard or certification.

Technology and traceability

Technology can provide traceability to both certification systems and arrangements that are not certified, by tracking events in the supply chain. While technology is not the only way to ensure traceability, and systems that play such a role can be differently designed to be fit for purpose (ISEAL Alliance, 2016), this research claims that in the context of marine plastic governance an online tracking system represents the most valuable approach. Among the solutions provided to increase traceability through technology, we encounter QR codes on final products and mobile technologies providing certified audit trails across the entire supply chain. The most valuable technologies are bi-directional and provide a traceability tool to all users in the chain, from scrapshops and waste collectors, to recycling facilities and producers. The Plastic Collective sets an example of best practice with its geotagging facilities based on a cloud-based platform, and the use of technology is becoming increasingly common (Table 9). However, not all supply chain providers use technology to improve transparency.

Certification bodies perform very differently under this criteria. Zero Plastic Oceans offers an application that can be customized to serve actors across the whole value chain. Even though the tool is new and limited information is available online, the developers are an experienced company in the sector and the application provides useful support. On the other hand, OceanCycle does not provide its value chain with technologies and tracking can be done either electronically or on paper, and Recycled material certification blue does not have any requirements about the use of technology for tracking but does provide products with a QR code.

Note that some organizations have developed a new recycling technology and are scaling it in developing countries, improving local collection and recycling systems. This is linked to sustainable development under an economic impact and did not influence the scoring for this criteria.

Table 9 provides examples of different approaches to traceability across arrangements.

Table 9. Example of programs and different approaches to traceability.

Type of arrangement	Program	Example
Certification	OBP Certification Program	Tracking can be done electronically or on paper, but an app is available to support users at each stage of the value chain.
Certification	OceanCycle	Tracking can be done electronically or on paper.
Credit scheme	Plastic Collective	Plastic Collective uses geotagging facilities that enable to map out the collection of plastic within a certain kilometers radio. In 2020 they strengthened their CRM systems and completed data migration onto a cloud based platform. With independent workspaces, all teams manage their processes, stakeholders management and communications on one platform. Through an SMS feature, the buy/sell transactions are verified by small business entrepreneurs. This feature is also enabled with a feedback/redressal mechanism for further clarifications/concerns/complaints. The SMS feature is available in 3 local languages to make it relevant in engagement for the informal sector.
Supply chain solutions	#tide	Traceability is not supported by any specific technology.

Chain of custody

By Chain of custody (CoC) we refer to “the process by which inputs and outputs and associated information are transferred, monitored and controlled as they move through each step in the relevant supply chain” (ISO, 2020), that in the case of marine plastic goes from collection to manufacturing of final products containing recovered materials. CoC systems are the application of the CoC model, and “include the complete set of documents and mechanisms used to verify the traceability between the verified unit of production and the claim about the final product” (ISEAL Alliance, 2016, p. 2). In practice, credible CoC certifications support the truthfulness of sustainability claims and of labels placed on products. Audits are performed at each stage of the supply chain, based on what is defined in the standard or mechanism.

Across all types of arrangement, two-thirds explicitly follow a CoC, while the rest mention traceability but without following the model. Among those that do follow a CoC, we differentiate the ones that do not specify the type of CoC (as detailed in Appendix E) and the ones they do. Finally, among the latter there is no uniformity, with the stricter ones choosing identity-preserved or segregation, and others mass balance model, with consequences about the claim the producer of the final product can make. In a mass balance model plastics from different sources can be mixed, therefore only claims for content of less than 100% are allowed. The stricter standard is the Standard for plastic from the hydrosphere, which rejects mass balance because it cannot guarantee the expected requirements of traceability.

The case of Verra Plastic Program is very specific because as the first credit standard available on the market, it did choose not to use a CoC because “it will likely be too burdensome to require that projects track the movement of the collected material beyond the destination that they sell the material to. We have heard from pilot projects on-the-ground that CoC requirements beyond this would be burdensome and unreasonable, especially on small-scale projects” (Verra, 2021, p. 13). There is a risk of leakage in absence of verifiable CoC, but being the standard in its pilot phase, it is not yet possible to verify if this lack of requirements will be a burden to traceability.

Table 10 provides examples of different CoC requirements across arrangements.

Table 10. Example of programs and different CoC requirements.

Type of arrangement	Program	Example
Scheme	Plastic Waste Reduction Standard	The adoption of a CoC “will likely be too burdensome [...] unreasonable, especially on small-scale projects.” (Verra, 2021)
Certification		Identity Preserved Model or segregation model. Mass balance is “out of scope because it cannot guarantee the expected requirements of traceability.”(43)
Certification	OceanCyle	Mass balance model.
Supply chain solutions	Parley Ocean Plastic	No chain of custody is mentioned.
Credit scheme	Plastics For Change	Mentions chain of custody, but not the type.

4.2.4. Integration with other schemes

Compliance with international frameworks assures commitment to reducing key issues, that are often interconnected and depend on each other, and fosters credibility by requiring certification schemes to follow international best practices (Gasser et al., 2018). The analysis shows no uniformity and limited compliance with the criteria, as described in Table 11.

Table 11. Integration with other schemes by arrangement type.

Arrangement	Best practice	Compliance	Example of best practice
Certifications and standards	Explicitly mention compliance with ISEAL best practices and other internationally recognized standards	Limited	These reference sources provide supporting information for organizations that apply this DNV standard. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO 9000:2015 - ISO/DIS 22095:2019(E) - ISO 14020: - ISO 14021:2016 - ISO/TS 17033:2019 - ISEAL Alliance – Sustainability claims Good practice guide - ISO 14040:2006 - ISO 14044:2006 - EN 15343:2007 - ISEAL, Chain of Custody Models and definitions - CEN/TR 15353:2007 - ISO/IEC Directives, Part 2 - ISO/IEC Guide 59:2019 - ISEAL Code of Good Practice for Setting Social and Environmental Standards - Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC
Supply chain solutions and credit schemes	Raw materials and final products are certified under established certification such as Global Recycling Standard (GRS), or UL – 2809 ECVP for Recycled Content, REACH or other sector-specific regulations.	Limited	Oceanworks: OBP certified #tide: under audit for OBP certification Plastic Collective: part of the pilot of Verra’s Plastic Program.

4.2.5. Third-party independent verification

Regarding standards and certifications, this criteria distinguishes between (Table 12):

- Standard setters that are also a verification body (OceanCycle and PFI Fareast);
- Standards that require an independent but predefined third-party to act as external auditor (Zero Plastic Oceans and PCU, The Ocean Cleanup and DNV GL);
- Standards that require third-party verification but leave to the adopter the option to choose the preferred auditing body (Verra Plastic Program).

As standard-setting can be done by any party, there is a risk of conflicts of interest, especially when the standard-setter and the certification body coincide (Dankers, 2003) or even when a pre-selected independent third-party is required.

Table 12. Overview of standards by standard setters and verification bodies.

Standard	Standard setter/ certification owner	Program	Verification body	Standard setter ≠ verification body	Any independent third-party allowed
Standard and certification	ZPO	OBP Neutralization Services Provider Standard	PCU	Yes	No
Standard and certification	ZPO	OBP Plastic Producers & Users Standard	PCU	Yes	No
Standard and certification	ZPO	OBP Collection Organization Standard	PCU	Yes	No
Standard and certification	ZPO	OBP Recycling Organization Standard	PCU	Yes	No
Certification	OceanCycle	OceanCycle certification	OceanCycle	No	No
Standard	The Ocean CleanUp	Ocean Plastic Standard	DNV	Yes	n/a
Standard and certification	PFI Fareast	Recycled material certification blue	PFI Fareast	No	No
Standard	VERRA	Plastic Waste Reduction standard	Any independent third-party	Yes	Yes
Standard	DNV	Public standard for plastics retrieved from the hydrosphere	DNV	Could not be assessed	

Among other types of arrangement, best practices are identified in organizations that are certified by independent third-parties. However, most of the supply chain initiatives are not certified, and the authenticity of the plastic they trade is not verified by an independent third-party, making it more difficult to prove the plastic's origin, especially in the final products that are manufactured using recycled plastic, but also in the generation of credits. This lack of external validation limits transparency and misses the opportunity to boost consumer confidence, something that is especially relevant to distinguish from other actors in a market that is steadily growing (The Circulate Initiative, 2021).

4.2.6. Cost of certifications or conversion measure for credits

This criteria maps transparency in the costs of getting certified or the cost of offsetting, specifically calculated as the conversion rate for plastic into credits.

In certifications, the cost of adoption is not publicly available for any standard. OBP and Verra publish their fees' structure, even though inspection and certification fees are available on consultation and calculated ad-hoc. Transparency would benefit if ranges of costs would be provided, for example concerning company size, structure, location of activities or type of activity. The other certification schemes do not provide any information, and pricing is available only on request.

Regarding supply chain solutions and credit schemes, the most critical issue encountered refers to the lack of uniform conversion measures. Even though all credit mechanisms provide on their website the conversion measure they adopt, this value is heterogeneous, and every scheme initiator can set its own conversion measure. Consequently, we observe misalignment in the offer, with the risk of incentivizing a market where price competition could reduce the value of the materials.

Examples of what described are provided in Table 13.

Table 13. Example of programs and different cost structures.

Type of arrangement	Program	Example
Certification	OBP Certification Program	Fee structure is available online in the documentation. The costs for organizations willing to become certified are composed of 2 elements: i) inspection and certification fees, and ii) OBP fees. OBP fees are explicit in the document, but inspection and certification fees are not available and calculated ad-hoc.
Certification	OceanCyle	Fees and fees structure are available ad-hoc and based on company characteristics.
Credit scheme	Plastics For Change	\$0.60 = 1 KG of ocean-bound plastic removed.
Credit scheme	ReSEA Project	8 € = 1 kg (equivalent to 50 plastic bottles of 500ml).

4.2.7. Presence in media

This criteria identifies differences in the use arrangements make of media and communication activities, and links it to the relevance of commercial adoption as a driving factor in SME's decisions (Section 5).

Table 14 provides examples of how programs perform differently under the criteria. Four scheme initiators (The Ocean Cleanup, Parley for the Oceans, Plastic Bank and, even if in smaller measure, Plastics For Change) have a significant online presence. However, and especially in the case of The Ocean Cleanup and Parley for the Oceans, this is due to the scale of all their activities, which exceeds the scope of this research. The Ocean Cleanup had a strong media coverage since the years it was founded, due to the innovative solutions it proposed to solve ocean plastic pollution. Parley for the Oceans has a strong network and it engages in advocacy, education and other activities. However, if we look specifically at the arrangements object of this paper, the Ocean Plastic Standard by The Ocean Cleanup has small coverage and strictly related to the final product the standard is certifying (sunglasses). On the other hand, Parley Ocean Plastic has more coverage but directly related to their collaboration with Adidas. The Plastic Bank is a well-known arrangement due to strong communication efforts and the collaboration with corporations such as Henkel. Other organizations, certifications and standards are still limitedly known to the public.

Table 14. Example of programs and visibility in media.

Type of arrangement	Program	Example
Standard	Ocean Plastic Standard	Limited visibility, but strong presence of The Ocean Cleanup as organization.
Supply chain solutions	Parley Ocean Plastic	Strong presence in most media as organization, and significant collaboration with Adidas.
Credit scheme	Cleanhub	Limited presence in media, 1 YouTube channel but inactive.

4.2.8. Overview of results

Figure 8 visually summarizes the results of the scoring systems. Every mechanism is scored for all the relevant criteria: green represents positive judgment (+1 in the scoring guide), red negative (-1), yellow neutral (0). The criteria that do not apply to the type of arrangement are indicated with grey color.

Arrangement	Program	Sub program	Monitoring and evaluating: Impact	Monitoring and evaluating: Reporting	Monitoring and evaluating: Continuous improvement	Definition of plastic targeted	Robust process	Technology for traceability	Chain of custody	Integration with other schemes	3rd party independent verification	Cost of certifications or conversion measure for credits	Visibility in media
OBP certification program	subp. 1*	a*	Yellow	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
		b*	Yellow	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
	subp. 2*	c*	Yellow	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
		d*	Yellow	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
OceanCycle certification			Yellow	Red	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Green	Yellow	Red	Red	Green
Recycled material certification blue			Red	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red	Red
Public standard for plastics retrieved from the hydrosphere			Grey	Grey	Red	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Yellow	Grey	Red
Ocean Plastic Standard			Yellow	Green	Red	Green	Yellow	Grey	Green	Green	Grey	Grey	Green
Plastic waste reduction standard			Grey	Grey	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Red	Green	Green	Green	Yellow
Cleanhub			Green	Yellow	Grey	Yellow	Grey	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red	Yellow
Parley Ocean Plastic			Yellow	Green	Grey	Yellow	Grey	Red	Red	Red	Red	Grey	Green
Oceanworks			Yellow	Red	Grey	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
OWP Ocean waste plastic			Red	Red	Grey	Green	Grey	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Grey	Grey	Yellow
#tide			Yellow	Red	Grey	Yellow	Grey	Red	Red	Green	Red	Grey	Yellow
Plastic Bank			Green	Green	Grey	Green	Grey	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green
The Plastic Collective			Yellow	Red	Grey	Red	Grey	Green	Red	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
Plastics For Change			Green	Green	Grey	Green	Grey	Green	Yellow	Green	Red	Green	Green
ReSEA Project			Green	Red	Grey	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow

Figure 8. Results of scoring system.

Abbreviations*. Subp. 1: OBP neutrality subprogram / Subp. 2 : OBP recycling subprogram / a: OBP Neutralization services provider standard / b: OBP Plastic producers & users standard / c: OBP Collection organization standard / d: OBP recycling organization standard.

It is possible to observe how programs perform unevenly, and no scheme provides an example of best practice under all criteria. As it will be discussed later, every solution presents different trade-offs and there is no ideal arrangement. Application strongly depends on the characterizes of potential adopters, their core activities and financial situation.

5. Results: the point of view of SMEs on certifications

To explicitly identify the barriers and enabling factors to the adoption of certification schemes for small and medium entrepreneurs, six semi-structured interviews and follow-up surveys were carried out. This section provides insights into the point of view of startups SMEs engaged in transformation of marine plastic. The scope is narrowed down to certifications schemes only, with a connection to related arrangements when relevant.

Table 15 provides a summary of the most important criteria identified by the interviewees and matches them to the scoring criteria in the previous section.

Table 15. Main criteria identified by SMEs and link with evaluation criteria.

Criteria from SMEs' perspective (interviews)	Arrangement evaluation criteria (database)	Main findings
Clarity about the terms ocean plastic and OBP	Definition of plastic targeted	Uncertainty around definitions mines the credibility of certifications and other arrangements.
Technology and traceability	Technology and traceability	Technologies providing traceability solutions are useful but not necessary.
Consumer's trust	Transparency and truthfulness (overarching)	SMEs believe their consumers trust them in their core business without need for certifications.
Commercial adoption	Presence in media	A leading certification adopted by big players in the market would foster acceptance.
Costs of adoption and return on investment	Costs of certifications or conversion measure for credits	Especially relevant for startups and small enterprises located in developing countries.
Independent auditing	Third-party certification	Especially relevant for organizations with limited budget.

Even though interviewees showed very limited awareness about existing instruments, all of them in principle agree on the importance of certifying the origin of their plastic material. They agree that *"we need some sort of regulation or something that ensures the origin of the plastic companies are using"*, but application is limited due to a variety of factors.

A first critic is related to the uncertainty around the definitions of ocean plastic. Even though most of them use the word ocean plastic in their communication activities, they reckon this is done because of the perceived value by the consumers, even though the plastic used for the products has sometimes not been in the water. Organizations that collect mostly OBP do not often use this same material for production, because *"the quality is too poor, so you have to*

just simply get rid of it, you can't make anything new". In those cases, the actual material is bought from external providers of recycled plastic from different (and not only marine) sources (for example regenerated nylon Econyl[®] or material from local plastic collectors). However, in some cases companies still claim their products to be made from ocean plastic. As an entrepreneur mentioned: *"lots of us love to call it ocean plastic because it sells"*. There is strong concern about the spread of greenwashing practices, even among the same organizations that criticize the system. All interviewees agreed on this, mentioning there is *"a lot of greenwashing going on with it. And I mean, it's always good to sell products, saying, hey, look, we've got recycled plastic in it"*.

Another important critic is made to the misuse of the words ocean plastic and OBP. Interviewees do not consider the terms apt to be used outside the academic environment, as in reality the plastic materials collected, recycled, and transformed are not necessarily at risk of entering the ocean. Moreover, most of the plastic used would probably not end in the ocean because likely to be incinerated. The critic to certifications links to the impossibility to prove the consequentiality between plastic wasted and ocean pollution, and therefore different actors believe that *"people shouldn't be allowed to call it ocean or ocean-bound plastics"* and *"it should be forbidden to use the word ocean if you know that 100% sure the plastic has never been in the ocean."*

Traceability is also an important topic. A reliable traceability system is highly valued, but there are doubts about the capacity of certifications to prove the origin of the materials. There is a lack of confidence from some entrepreneurs in the reliability of certifications: in their experience *"there are not even requirements to have photos on file or GPS location tagging or anything, they basically give you one A4 sheet of paper, where you can claim anything"* and *"I have never heard of anyone not passing it"*. These doubts link to the importance of technology in ensuring traceability. A geo-mapping system that makes the information available to consumers is more valuable than a certification that requires documents to be filled out but that cannot control all the materials collected (or used) during the validity of the claim. For instance, a system that communicates the location *"is much more charming than having the OBP logo on the product, because it actually takes you to the location"* and *"that's something that's also interesting for the people and even builds up more emotional connection"*. A connection is made with the company's reputation. Small enterprises and startups strongly believe that the relationship they have built with customers is strong enough if they invest in transparency, and this reputation can replace the value of a certification. *"Our priority to be as transparent as possible and [...] we don't feel like we need the certificate or anything else in order to be more trustworthy"*. On the other hand, *"big companies who don't have smaller communities or don't build up a whole sense of trying to make their work traceable, are instead needing something like a certificate to be trustworthy"*.

More than compliance with technical criteria, such as impact reporting or CoC, the highest value is given by the claim that the program entitles. Schemes that allow making a certain claim based on the origin of plastic, even if not certified, are preferred if they enable a better financial return. We derive that commercial adoption is the main enabling factor for SMEs to adopt a

certain arrangement. Even though they agree with the potential value of certifications, SMEs are not likely to adopt them widely until the big players in the market start endorsing them and give them notoriety. The importance of the arrangement does not lie in the certification itself, but the visibility it can give a brand in the market. As entrepreneurs mentioned, *“you want to make really sure that the certificate that you are joining will be the new standard”* and *“in [COUNTRY], at the moment nobody pays us more because it's OBP certified”*. This means that at the moment, certifications do not facilitate a premium price for products. Or, more precisely, a premium price can potentially be charged without the adoption of a certification.

High costs are a strong deterrent for smaller organizations. This barrier can be linked to two elements: the possibility of independent auditing and the value of collection activities. If a certification allows the organization to choose an independent auditor, there is a significant increase in trust and affordability for companies with a limited budget. The existing certifications work with selected certification bodies, in what has been defined by an entrepreneur as *“a self-enforcing system”*, significantly limiting accessibility for low budget enterprises and also mining credibility of the audit. Regarding the value of collection activities and specifically from small collectors' point of view, credit schemes have an interesting value because they can finance clean-up activities by paying more for the waste than the traditional system. Consequentially, there is a positive effect on local economies and workers, and more funding becomes available to invest in recycling and production activities. However, this does not necessarily mean that the organization agrees in principle with the institution of a credit system for plastic offsets, but that in some cases where budget is very limited, the advantages from the point of view of the return of investment prevail.

6. Results: Synthesis

Results differ significantly according to the type of arrangement and the size of the potential adopters. Certifications and standards are more apt to organizations that operate on a medium-large scale. Consumers are savvier than in the past and have expectations towards the brands they choose, and certifications represent an added value for them. Even though the same reasoning applies to SMEs, for whom certifications have the potential to provide trust when the company's presence in the market is still limited, there are significant constraints. SMEs that transform marine plastic tend to build consumer trust and credibility with transparency in their operations, and they believe certifications do not bring them additional value. Certifications do not guarantee a return on investment, especially because claims are not yet widely commercially adopted and known by consumers.

For small collector and recycling organizations, credit schemes might provide better financial opportunities, as they pay more for collection activities and therefore enable small organizations to increase the scale of their operation. But credit systems present a set of limitations that cannot be analyzed in detail in this paper. Main tradeoffs relate to transparency and traceability, as most of those arrangements do not follow a chain of custody and are not yet externally verified, creating serious doubts about their effectiveness in solving the marine plastic pollution issue. Additionally, there is a strong need for regulation about how to gain credits, emit them, and about conversion systems. While in the carbon market there is a standard, meant as one unit of carbon offset credit equals one metric ton of CO₂, there is no such definition for plastic, and not for ocean plastic or OBP. Another further limitation is related to the unclarity of the term plastic neutrality. Due to the lack of a standard conversion rate and the possibility organizations have to purchase a predetermined number of credits that do not necessarily cover their full plastic footprint, the risk of greenwashing and misuse of the term is significant.

Finally, companies have a more practical point of view regarding certifications (they give limited importance to criteria such as stakeholder engagement and integration with other schemes), but, on the other hand, all those elements are fundamental for policymakers. They are needed for the creation of a homogeneous set of regulations that can set the basis for the system to function and develop.

7. Discussion

The combination of desk and empirical research allowed to address the issues and limitations related to the current landscape of existing arrangements for marine plastic governance. Furthermore, the analysis of the point of view of SMEs highlighted how the needs of organizations significantly differ according to size, maturity, and specific activity they are engaged in. Findings indicate a variety of elements that affect the effectiveness of the existing instruments.

First, as discussed in section 4.2.1, real and trackable monitoring and evaluating systems are missing for most of the arrangements. This reflects the impossibility to have a proper overview of the real impact of those schemes. For example, when looking at credits it is unknown how many companies are buying credits and how many credits have been issued globally and regionally. Moreover, the actual role of those schemes in the creation of a market for plastic waste that contributes to stopping the production of virgin plastic is still unclear. Regarding certifications, this happens because claims can be assigned to products not completely made of ocean and OBP, again leaving space for greenwashing or consumers' misunderstanding. For crediting, the risk is that companies use the claim of plastic reduction or plastic neutrality without substantially changing their business (WWF, 2021). Supporters of the system discuss that the plastic crediting system targets companies for the part of plastic use that cannot be reduced in the value chain, and only after companies have scanned and adopted other methods to reduce their plastic footprint. However, in a system that lacks transparency and uniformity, it is not possible yet to prove that companies are pursuing these strategies and to what extent.

Similar reasoning applies to the concept of additionality. Additionality means that collection and recycling occur resulting from the implementation of a new arrangement. The newness of the system and the lack of monitoring and reporting constitute a barrier in proving additionality, as most of the communities where those supply chains are established already have a collecting system, even if informal, and new mechanisms often rely on it, even though providing innovation and infrastructure.

Limitations of this research are linked to the complexity of the environmental problem object of the study. Even though it was possible to group arrangements under certain umbrella definitions, each sub-group shows significant differences in operations, organization of activities and governance systems. Even though best practices were identified and it was possible to rate arrangements under certain criteria, it is still difficult to map with certainty the current landscape of claims and credits related to marine plastic. Another constraint of this research refers to the impossibility to assess the level of stakeholder engagement in the development of standards and certification schemes. In a multi-stakeholder process, every stakeholder should be part of the design process of the arrangement. However, it is not possible to assess the level of participation only from the information available online, and direct questions to governing bodies and other stakeholders would be needed to provide

comprehensive answers. In the results section 4.2.2, the only example of transparent stakeholder engagement was highlighted.

Interviews with SMEs have shown that the system is not ready yet to provide the support needed by small companies, differently from what happens with more established certifications that respond to other environmental or social issues, for example Fair Trade. Moreover, at the time being arrangements that focus on marine plastic only do not have the characteristics needed to compete with programs that tackle plastic without setting their scope to the marine environment. Ocean and OBP arrangements seem to be creating a set of overlapping yet inconsistent tools that do not work together, dilute the value of the system, and prevent a few of them from becoming the guiding standards. This happens because arrangements do not grant additional transparency to small-medium realities, and they lack wide support from big corporations with the potential to set market directions. This significantly limits the value they provide, their credibility, and their ability to have a large-scale impact.

While literature is growing, little attention is still given to the development of a guide for harmonization of existing private arrangements. Literature is focusing on specific governance arrangements at different scales, for example Landon-Lane (2018) and his proposal of an industry-targeted code of conduct (Landon-Lane, 2018), or the Global Treaty for Plastic currently under development and meant to provide a “comprehensive governance strategy to address prevention as a primary approach and to ensure sustainable management of plastics throughout the value chain” (Raubenheimer & Urho, 2020). Emerging studies are also researching the effectiveness of different systems on global or local scale (Lee, 2021), and they identify best practices but without narrowing the scope to marine plastic (The Circulate Initiative, 2021). This study goes deeper into the analysis of instruments and provides a practical evaluation system of the overarching landscape. The existing landscape of private governance arrangements is also linked to companies’ needs, and the results could be used in the future to set the directions for a standardized system that not only aims at maximizing debris reduction, but that also fits companies’ requirements for enhanced effectiveness of those tools. The findings in this paper could provide a starting point for the development of such a system, by setting criteria that should be taken into consideration and highlighting elements that need improvement. Based on that, it would be fruitful to develop an international standard resulting from the harmonization process of various instruments. This standard should follow the guidelines provided by established institutions in other sectors, and by the best practices identified in this research. It should be assessed by international bodies and regulators and applied to individual mechanisms, while adoption should be kept voluntary, to guarantee flexibility and added value to certified organizations.

Future research would benefit from more interviews with SMEs and corporates, as our sample was limited. Considering that private and public attention to the issue is growing and that different businesses have diverse needs, requirements and expectations of companies deserves further examination. Additionally, it would be interesting to compare established

arrangements for plastic such as the Global Recycling Standard (GRS) with emerging ones that focus their scope on marine plastic, to use them as a benchmark for improvement.

Finally, the transition towards more effective solutions to marine debris cannot be driven only by one scheme. Organizations need to have access to various supporting mechanisms that work together and reinforce each other. And to prove effective, those solutions for cleaner oceans must be aligned, harmonized, and work under comparable requirements and conditions.

8. Conclusion

The recycling industry is relatively new and public attention to marine plastic has recently grown at an incredible rate. While in the past there was a lack of awareness about the environmental threat of plastic in marine environments, now that interest and consciousness have flourished, a melting pot of instruments has emerged from the private sector and civil society, but without proper regulation. Most of the arrangements are still not well-known or accepted, and more importantly, they operate in a fragmented landscape that seems to fail to address the problem consistently. For example, certifications do not certify under the same requirements and conditions, limiting comparability and evaluation possibilities. Arrangements also have different approaches to the problem and diverse objectives. While certifications are meant to validate the origin of a certain material, the creation of supply chains plays a fundamental role in engaging the traditionally informal sector of plastic collection and recycling.

This paper provides an analysis of programs, identifies their roles and limitations and addresses the needs of SMEs in relation to those schemes. It emerges that existing mechanisms are not yet fit to provide overarching solutions to small entrepreneurs, and claims ocean and OBP specific are not able to create added value, foster consumer's trust and give small companies additional credibility. However, there is potential for improvement. The recent establishment of a standard for plastic credits, for example, might represent a fundamental step towards harmonization. This research states that the integration of a set of best practices into existing arrangements would facilitate uniform acceptance and application of marine plastic claims in business. At the same time, those arrangements have to be tailored to the needs of different realities in terms of activity, size, and location of the adopter. To conclude, no instrument is a panacea for the wicked problem of marine plastic pollution and different supporting mechanisms are needed to fill in existing gaps, reinforce each other and respond to a variety of market needs and situations.

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Programs and organizations reviewed

Program or organization	Website
OBP Certification Program	https://www.obpcert.org/
OceanCycle	https://oceancycle.co/
Recycled material certification blue	https://pfi.hk/footwear-and-leather-testing-services/recycled-material-certification-blue/
Public standard for plastics retrieved from the hydrosphere	https://www.dnv.com/se/services/chain-of-custody-standard-for-plastics-retrieved-from-the-hydrosphere-188396
Ocean Plastic Standard	https://theoceancleanup.com/updates/introducing-the-ocean-plastic-standard/ https://theoceancleanup.com/
Plastic waste reduction standard	https://verra.org/project/plastic-program/
Cleanhub	https://www.cleanhub.io/
Parley Ocean Plastic	https://www.parley.tv/#fortheoceans
Oceanworks	http://oceanworks.co/
Ocean Waste Plastics	https://www.oceanwasteplastics.com/
#tide	https://tide.earth/
Plastic Bank	https://plasticbank.com/
The Plastic Collective	https://www.plasticcollective.co/
Plastics For Change	https://www.plasticsforchange.org/
ReSEA Project	https://www.reseaproject.com/

Appendices

Appendix A

ISEAL Credibility Principles.

Those criteria are provided by the foundation of the International Social and Environmental Accreditation and Labelling Alliance (ISEAL ALLIANCE), a non-governmental organization with the mission to strengthen sustainability standard systems that benefit people and the environment. ISEAL developed a Code of Good Practice for Setting Social and Environmental Standards that supports the development of standards that are “relevant and transparent and that reflect a balance of stakeholder interests” (ISEAL, 2014, p. 3). 10 Credibility Principles are included in the code to underpin effective practices for sustainability standard systems.

WWF’s Principles for Effective and Credible Certification Schemes.

WWF actively participates in the development of the Impact Code by ISEAL, and also provides a set of principles that respond to the need for generic methodologies and approaches to standards, certifications and labeling, to ensure consistency and comparability across voluntary standard-setting initiatives (WWF, 2009).

Table A.1. Guiding principles for the creation of criteria for comparison and evaluation of marine plastic governance arrangements. Adapted from WWF (2009) and ISEAL (2014).

Principle	ISEAL Credibility Principles	WWF Principles for Effective and Credible Certification Schemes	Adapted description
Sustainability	✓		Standards scheme owners clearly define and communicate their sustainability objectives and approach to achieving them. Sustainability objectives are articulated in terms of intended outcomes and impacts. There is a monitoring and evaluation system to evaluate the effectiveness of the standard in achieving the sustainability objectives.
Improvement / Commitment to continuous improvement	✓	✓	The scheme should include monitoring and review processes, which recognize the need for better practices and the commitment to continual improvement. Those systems demonstrate progress towards the intended outcomes.
Relevance	✓		Standards are fit for purpose. They address the most significant sustainability impacts of a product, process, business, or service; only include requirements that contribute to their objectives; reflect best scientific understanding and relevant international norms, and are adapted where necessary to local conditions.
Rigour	✓		Standards are set at a performance level that results in measurable progress towards
Engagement / Meaningful and equitable stakeholder participation	✓	✓	Decision-making procedures take into account a balanced and representative group of stakeholders. At what level depends on the stage of the certification process.
Impartiality	✓		Standards systems identify and mitigate conflicts of interest throughout their operations, particularly in the assurance process and in governance. Transparency, accessibility and balanced representation contribute to impartiality.

Transparency	✓	✓	The scheme's requirements, development and content of the standard, as well as results of certification and accreditation reports (impact information), should be made available in the public domain.
Truthfulness / Traceability	✓	✓	The claim must be truthful, verifiable, not misleading. A robust process allows tracing of the product along the supply chain to ensure that the claims are reflected in the product's characteristics from its point of production.
Accessibility	✓		To reduce barriers to implementation, standards systems minimize costs and overly burdensome requirements. They facilitate access to information about meeting the standard, training, and financial resources to build capacity throughout supply chains and for actors within the standards system.
Efficiency	✓		Standards systems refer to or collaborate with other credible schemes to improve consistency and efficiency in standards content and operating practices. They improve their viability through the application of sound revenue models and organizational management strategies.
Commitment to reducing key issues		✓	Commitment to reducing key economic, environmental and social impacts of the problem to be tackled.
Result-oriented		✓	Certification must be based – as much as possible - on objective, scientifically defined and measurable performance.
Compliant with International frameworks		✓	The structure of the scheme, including certification, accreditation and verification processes, should comply with existing international norms developed by ISO, the International Accreditation Forum (IAF) and the ISEAL Alliance.
Third-party independent certification		✓	Independent third-party certification verifies compliance with the standards. Multiple and international Certification Bodies should be accredited by the certification scheme to discourage an exclusive Certification Body affecting the audits.
Relevant scale		✓	The scheme should drive improvement at scale to avoid continued widespread damage to natural assets and to maximize the effect of the certification scheme. Needs to be concentrated on achieving real change.

Appendix B

The concept of OBP has been embraced by most of the NGOs, social enterprises and organizations operating in the reduction of ocean pollution. This definition originated from a paper by Jenna Jambeck (2015) (J. R. Jambeck et al., 2015), where the authors estimate the mass of land-based plastic waste entering the ocean. They focus on mismanaged plastic waste generated annually by populations living within 50 km of a coast worldwide that can potentially enter the ocean as marine debris. Plastic waste is intended as litter or waste not captured and dumped on the land. In the list of countries analyzed, the top contributors are mostly middle-income countries that are experiencing fast economic growth but that have not been able yet to develop effective waste management infrastructure, capable to handle the increase in waste generation that comes along with economic growth (Jenna R. Jambeck, 2015). The concept of OBP generates from this study and has been so widely adopted because it establishes a link between the harm plastic is doing to waters and sea life, and the sources of the problem. It also gives an academic explanation as to why the majority of the plastic collection sites used by many of the organizations creating the marine plastic schemes are located in coastal communities in developing countries.

Appendix C

Ocean Bound Plastic Certifications classify the traditional concept of OBP by Jambek (2015) into three categories (Ocean Bound Plastic Certification Scheme, 2020):

1. POTENTIAL OBP
Generic category of mismanaged plastic waste within 50km from the coast
2. WATERWAYS OBP
OBP carried by rivers, it covers OBP from 200m from riverbanks and OBP inside the river itself.
3. SHORELINE OBP
OBP present very close to shores, 200m from the tide line, on the beach and in the first 100m in the sea.

Appendix D

Oceanworks defines seven plastic collection areas (Oceanworks, n.d.):

1. OFFSHORE
Material far from shore accumulated floating “gyres.” The material is primarily HDPE, as it floats, and represents a fraction of the plastics that enter the ocean each year.
2. NEARSHORE
Material suspended in the shallow areas of the ocean that are close to shore. This category also includes fishing net recovery and intervention programs.
3. WATERWAY
Material found in streams, rivers and other waterways flowing towards the ocean.
4. COASTAL
Material that has washed up onto beaches and coastlines.
5. OCEAN-BOUND
Material collected from communities with no formal waste management within 50 km of the shoreline. This catchment area was first utilized in research by marine debris expert, Jenna Jambeck, in evaluating the source of plastic waste entering the ocean.
6. AVERTED
Material collected from communities with mismanaged waste at more than 50km from the shoreline. This is plastic that, if not responsibly recovered on land and reutilized for production, would likely remain in the environment, causing pollution.
7. POST CONSUMER RECYCLED (PCR)
Material that has been used by consumers and reached its end of life AND is diverted from the landfill through a formal or an informal recycling program to be reutilized in future production.

8. POST INDUSTRIAL RECYCLED (PIR)

Material generated from the original manufacturing process that does not end up being used in the final product. This material is diverted from the landfill to be reutilized in future production.

Oceanworks categories 1-7 fall under the umbrella of post-consumer recycled content. Categories 1-5 fall under the umbrella of “ocean plastic.”

Appendix E

Arrangements analyzed in this paper follow three main types of CoC (ISEAL Alliance, 2016):

1. PRODUCT SEGREGATION
2. IDENTITY PRESERVATION
3. MASS BALANCE

With a segregation model, the CoC follows the product through each part of the chain, and it verifies that the product comes from a certified source. The certified product is kept separate from non-certified sources at each stage of the supply chain, but it permits the mixing of certified products or ingredients from different sources that are certified by the same standards.

An Identity preservation model goes one step further by not allowing the mixing of certified products, so it is possible to trace individual products back to a specific production site and batch if used through the whole supply chain. With a mass balance system, certified and non-certified materials can be mixed. The exact volume of certified material entering the operation is controlled, and then an equivalent volume of material leaving the operation can be sold as certified. This is common for products where segregation is impossible and results and claims of contains a certain percentage of certified ingredients.

Supplementary Material

Scoring system

Guiding criteria	Criteria	Description	Arrangements (valid for)	Scale	Explanation of scale	Arrangements (valid for)	Scale	Explanation of scale	Arrangements (valid for)	Scale	Explanation of scale				
Sustainability, continuous improvement, result-oriented, relevant scale, relevance	Monitoring and evaluating systems - Impact	Does the impact include all the elements of sustainable development? Is the measurable impact of the arrangement publicly available and easily accessible? Is the measurable impact detailed and can it evolution be tracked with the information publicly available?	CERTIFICATIONS, CREDIT SCHEMES, SUPPLY CHAIN SOLUTIONS	-1	The scheme only focuses on the environmental impact of reducing plastic pollution. No information is publicly available about how this impact is tracked and measured.	STANDARDS	n/a								
	Monitoring and evaluating systems - Reporting	Are there annual (or to-date) reports publicly available online, on the website of the organization and/or on other sources?		-1	There is no report publicly available.							0	Annual or up-to-date reports can be easily requested via an online form.	1	Annual reports are publicly available and easily accessible online.
	Monitoring and evaluating systems - Continuous improvement	Is there a publicly available process to revise standards and criteria in place? Are periodic reviews scheduled? Is the award of a certification valid for a specific and limited period of time? OR Is there a specific plastic crediting period?		-1	There is no publicly available process to revise standards and criteria in place and there is no mention of the time period the uptaker is entitled to the use of the claim.							0	There is no publicly available process to revise standards and criteria in place, but there is a specific period of time for the validity of the certification.	1	There is a clear procedure to revise the standard and criteria in place and reviews are scheduled, combined with the right to use the claim for a limited period of time.
Transparency, truthfulness/traceability, accessibility	Definition of plastic targeted	Is there a clarity about what type of plastic is targeted? Is the definition of what type of plastic is targeted aligned with literature? Is the definition used referenced and justified? Does the scheme clearly target recyclable, non-recyclable plastic, or both?	STANDARDS, CERTIFICATIONS, CREDIT SCHEMES, SUPPLY CHAIN SOLUTIONS	-1	There is no clear and accessible definition of what kind of plastic or ocean plastic is targeted. There is no alignment with commonly used standards or definitions.	CREDIT SCHEMES, SUPPLY CHAIN SOLUTIONS	n/a								
	Robust process	Is there a clear definition of requirements for companies to adopt the scheme? Are guiding documents regarding the certification process available? Are there publicly available clear definitions of the procedures for companies to adopt the scheme (or the company has to contact the scheme setter to get information)? Is there a clear definition of what aspects of the supply chain the arrangement covers? Is the publicly disclosed information comprehensible, credible and comparable?		-1	No documentation about the scheme's requirements and procedures is available. Information can be accessed only by getting in touch with the organization.							0	It is clear what steps of the supply chain the scheme covers. Scheme's requirements and procedures are explained on the website of the organization, but detailed information is provided only by getting in touch with the organization.	1	Detailed scheme's requirements and procedures are accessible from the website of the organization. It is clear what steps of the supply chain the scheme covers.
	Technology and traceability	Does the scheme initiator provide technologies to its users? Are technologies used to facilitate traceability in the supply chain? Is the tracking available bi-directionally (reciprocal transparency)?		-1	Tracking is done manually or without a specific methodology. There is no specification of any technology used in any stage of the supply chain.							0	The organization mentions the use of technology but not clearly how it can be used and to which stakeholder or stage of the value chain it is addressed.	1	The organization created an innovative technology and uses it as a basis for the development of the supply chain, or the organization uses a technology for tracking of its operations. The technology is bi-directional (all the actors in the value chain benefit from its use).
	Chain of custody	Does the arrangement follow a verifiable chain of custody? Is the chain of custody clearly explained in the information publicly available? Is type of chain of custody specified?		-1	The scheme does not mention any chain of custody.							0	The scheme is based on chain of custody, but not detailed information is provided.	1	The scheme is based on the chain of custody, and which type is specified.
Commitment to reducing key issues, efficiency, rigor, compliant with international framework	Integration with other schemes	Does the program explicitly address alignment with other established programs or standards? Does the program explicitly follow ISEAL best practices?	STANDARDS, CERTIFICATIONS, CREDIT SCHEMES, SUPPLY CHAIN SOLUTIONS	-1	The arrangements do not mention any compliance with other frameworks or quality certifications. Certification and standards do not explicitly mention ISEAL guidelines.	CREDIT SCHEMES, SUPPLY CHAIN SOLUTIONS	n/a								
				0	Compliance with other standards is mentioned, but not necessarily related to ocean plastic certifications or standards, and ISEAL guidelines are not specifically mentioned.							1	Compliance with other established programs or standards is mentioned. For credit schemes or supply chain solutions the arrangement is also certified by specific ocean plastic certifications or standards, or it is currently being audited. Certification and standards explicitly mention ISEAL guidelines.		
				Third-party independent verification	Does the arrangement require third-party verification? Is the third-party verification body independent from the standard setter? Is the arrangement certified by an independent third-party? Is the independent third-party identified?							-1	There is not third-party verification requirement.	0	The standard/certification requires the adopters to be verified by a third-party, and the standard setter is the verification body.
Ad-hoc criteria	Cost of certifications or conversion measure for credits	Is there information about the cost of getting certified available on the organization's website? Is the conversion measure for the credit scheme available on the organization's website?	CERTIFICATIONS, STANDARDS	-1	No information about costs of getting certified is easily accessible and publicly available online.	CREDIT SCHEMES	n/a								
				0	The fee structure is publicly available and the certification fees are communicated, however the inspection and certification fees are calculated ad-hoc for each company and there is no range of costs available.							1	Structure and fees are available, and even if the final cost is provided ad-hoc post consultation, a range of costs depending on variables such as company size is provided.		
				Visibility in media	To what extent is the arrangement or the initiator visible in the most common social media (number of followers in FB, Instagram, LinkedIn and availability of webinars and YouTube videos)? Is information about the mechanism easily accessible by the public? Is the standard high ranked in Google Search (7 keywords: ocean plastic, ocean plastic certification, marine plastic, ocean-bound plastic, plastic credits, ocean plastic credits, ocean bound plastic product)? Does the standard has a strong presence in a varied range of media?							-1	The scheme has limited visibility and presence in media. Average presence: possible to find information, but not on a variety of channels, and the mechanism is not engaged in relevant marketing activities (including social media).	0	Good coverage in the media such as website, Google search and articles and grey literature, and the organization engages in additional channels such as social media, podcasts, youtube channels.